

D4.1

Report on specification, development and provision of the Blockchain functionality and smart contracts

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Authors	Ferdinando Bosco (ENG), Vincenzo Croce (ENG), Ámbar Tenorio-Fornés (FCF), Filisia Melissari (SYN), Aggelos Orfanoudakis (SYN), Nelly Leligou (INTRA), Iago Fernandez-Cedron (UPM)

Reviewers Andrew King (MMU), Hugues Vinet (IRCAM)

Abstract

This deliverable presents the concept of Blockchain Technology, NFTs and related Web3 technologies and how these technologies can be applied in the context of Creative Industries, for empowering creators by endowing them with greater ownership and control over their digital assets.

All the DAFNE+ Platform components, based on blockchain technology and smart contracts are described in this document, reporting the core concepts, the architectures, the main functionalities, and the technical specifications.

Keywords

Blockchain, Non-Fungible Tokens (NFTs), Marketplace, Revenue Models, Web3

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			Iago Fernandez-Cedron (UPM)
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Abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
DAO	Decentralized Autonomous Organization
DApp	Decentralized Application
DeFi	Decentralized Finance
NFT	Non-Fungible Token
PoS	Proof of Stake
PoW	Proof of Work
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
WP	Work Package

1 Executive summary

Blockchain is a disruptive and revolutionary technology for the Creative Industries' world, able to create new opportunities for artists and collectors.

For this reason, blockchain technology is a core part of the DAFNE+ Platform and all the main functionalities for the management of Digital Assets (including NFT creation) are based on it.

Within the DAFNE+ Platform there are three blockchain-based applications: The Blockchain Realm, the NFT tool and the Marketplace.

All these components were implemented following the user requirements and needs, identified in WP2 leveraging on the benefits that this technology can offer to them.

The Blockchain Realm consists of a blockchain-ready framework able to:

- make simple and fast interactions with the blockchain networks (Polygon and Ethereum)
- facilitate the deployment and integration of Smart Contracts
- provide APIs to with core blockchain features (NFTs, Tokens, Smart Contracts methods, Monitoring, etc.)

The NFT tool, is a dedicated component for facilitating the creation, management, and sale of NFTs within the DAFNE+ Platform and together with the DAFNE+ NFT Marketplace it plays the crucial role of allowing the NFT creators to publish and monetize their artistic productions.

The NFT Marketplace is essentially a virtual place where digital artists and creators can advertise and sell their work, while being remunerated fairly.

All these components were integrated in the overall DAFNE+ Platform and released in a first version that will be evaluated and tested in the first round of pilots.

2 Introduction

2.1 Purpose and context of the document

This document reports on the activities carried out under tasks T4.1, T4.2 and T4.3 in the first period of the project.

The main goal of this document is to describe the blockchain technology and its applications in the creative industries domain, with a focus on the implementation of the blockchain-based applications for the DAFNE+ Platform: The Blockchain Realm, the NFT tool and the Marketplace.

The document provides an overview on the technology, the architecture and the main functionalities offered by the components and how the blockchain technology plays a key role on the digital asset management through smart contracts and Non-Fungible Tokens (NFTs).

2.2 Document structure

In addition to the Executive Summary and this introductory chapter, the document is structured into 3 additional chapters:

- Chapter 3 provides an introduction to the concept of blockchain, the main differences between blockchain 1.0 and 2.0 as well as Layer 1 and Layer 2 and finally the potential applications of blockchain in the creative industries.
- Chapter 4 describes how blockchain technology was used in the implementation of the DAFNE+ Platform and focuses on the description of the blockchain-based DAFNE+ components implemented in the first version of the DAFNE+ Platform: Blockchain Realm, the NFT tool and the NFT Marketplace.
- Chapter 5 concludes this document.

2.3 Dependencies to-from other WPs

Tasks T4.1, T4.2, and T4.3 considered all the use cases, requirements and scenarios defined in WP2 and the DAFNE+ Architecture as reference for the implementation of the components.

For the definition of the smart contract for revenue models, the input from WP6 was also useful.

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The output of these tasks is important for T4.5, in which the overall DAFNE+ Platform will be integrated and released as well as the WP5, where these components and blockchain features will be tested and evaluated within different scenarios.

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3 Blockchain Technology

3.1 Introduction and main concepts

Blockchain technology has emerged as a disruptive innovation as the underlying technology for cryptocurrencies like Bitcoin and has developed with many applications beyond its original purpose.

At its core, a blockchain is a distributed ledger system designed to record and secure transactions across a network of computers. Unlike traditional centralized systems, a blockchain operates in a decentralized manner, utilizing a network of nodes (computers) to validate and record transactions.

The architecture of the blockchain technology leverages on the following key attributes:

1. Decentralization

One of the foundational principles of blockchain is decentralization. In contrast to centralized systems controlled by a single entity, blockchain networks are maintained by a distributed network of nodes. Each node has a copy of the entire blockchain ledger, ensuring that no single point of failure exists. This decentralization enhances security, resilience, and trust in the system.

2. Consensus Mechanisms

To validate and add transactions to the blockchain, a consensus mechanism is employed. The most common mechanisms include Proof of Work (PoW) and Proof of Stake (PoS). PoW requires miners to solve complex mathematical puzzles to validate transactions, while PoS relies on validators who "stake" cryptocurrency as collateral to confirm transactions. These mechanisms ensure that only legitimate transactions are added to the ledger.

3. Immutability

Once a transaction is recorded on the blockchain, it becomes extremely challenging to alter or delete. The immutability of blockchain data is a fundamental feature that provides a high level of security and trust. It is

achieved through cryptographic hashing, where transactions are grouped into blocks, and each block is linked to the previous one.

4. Transparency

Blockchains are open and transparent by design. Anyone can view the entire transaction history, promoting trust and accountability. This transparency is particularly valuable in applications where trust is critical, such as supply chain management and financial services.

3.1.1 Blockchain 1.0 – Bitcoin

Bitcoin stands as the pioneering cryptocurrency and the foundational blockchain that started the blockchain revolution.

The inception of Bitcoin traces back to a whitepaper titled "Bitcoin: A Peer-to-Peer Electronic Cash System" [1] authored by the enigmatic figure known as Satoshi Nakamoto in October 2008. Bitcoin's official genesis moment occurred on January 3, 2009, when Nakamoto mined the inaugural block, recognized as the "genesis block."

Bitcoin is fundamentally a digital currency engineered for peer-to-peer transactions. It empowers individuals to directly exchange value, bypassing the need for intermediaries such as traditional banks or payment processors. Transactions within the Bitcoin network are meticulously recorded on a publicly accessible ledger known as the blockchain.

The underpinning of Bitcoin is a decentralized network, comprising nodes (computers) dispersed globally. This decentralization ensures that no single entity, governmental authority, or organization wields control over the Bitcoin ecosystem. Bitcoin relies on the PoW to validate transactions and safeguard the network.

Bitcoin's supply is intentionally capped at 21 million coins. This finite supply diverges from conventional fiat currencies, which can be produced in unrestricted quantities. The concept of scarcity is imprinted into Bitcoin's code and plays a pivotal role in its identity as a store of value.

Bitcoin employs advanced cryptographic techniques to fortify the security of transactions and to guarantee their immutability. Once a transaction finds its place on the blockchain, it becomes exceedingly arduous to modify or erase, instilling confidence in the system's integrity.

Transactions within the Bitcoin network exhibit pseudonymity rather than absolute anonymity. They are linked to alphanumeric addresses rather than real-world identities. Although this design offers a measure of privacy, it does not ensure complete anonymity, as blockchain analysis can potentially unveil transaction patterns.

Bitcoin has earned recognition as "Digital Gold" and a reliable store of value. Analogous to precious metals like gold, Bitcoin is seen as a hedge against inflation and economic turbulence. Its controlled supply and decentralized architecture bolster its stature as a store of value.

Over the years, Bitcoin has transcended its niche beginnings to emerge as a global financial phenomenon. It has achieved acceptance as a method of payment for products and services across diverse industries. Furthermore, Bitcoin has evolved into an investment asset, attracting institutional and retail investors to participate in its burgeoning market.

Despite its remarkable achievements, Bitcoin confronts challenges like scalability and the energy consumption attributed to the PoW consensus mechanism. The Bitcoin community tirelessly collaborates on enhancements and scalability solutions to tackle these issues. Additionally, discussions regarding regulatory frameworks for cryptocurrencies persist in numerous nations.

3.1.2 Blockchain 2.0 – Ethereum

Ethereum, often referred to as "Blockchain 2.0," is a transformative blockchain that builds upon the principles introduced by Bitcoin and extends the capabilities of blockchain technology in profound ways. To understand Ethereum fully, it is essential to explore its history, its distinctions from Bitcoin, and the concept of Blockchain 2.0.

Ethereum was conceptualized and developed by a talented programmer named Vitalik Buterin in 2014 [2], and the network officially launched on July 30, 2015. The genesis of Ethereum was rooted in addressing perceived limitations in Bitcoin. While Bitcoin primarily aimed to create a digital currency, Ethereum sought to provide a more versatile platform for Decentralized Applications (DApps) and smart contracts.

The main differences from Bitcoin are:

1. Purpose and Functionality

Bitcoin was created as a digital currency and a store of value, focusing primarily on peer-to-peer electronic cash transactions. Ethereum, on the other hand, was designed as a general-purpose blockchain platform that enables developers to build and deploy DApps and smart contracts.

2. Smart Contracts

One of Ethereum's most important features is its support for smart contracts. Smart contracts are self-executing contracts with the terms of the agreement directly encoded into code. Bitcoin, while programmable to an extent, was not designed with the same level of flexibility as Ethereum. Smart contracts on Ethereum enable a wide range of applications, from Decentralized Finance (DeFi) to supply chain management and more.

3. Turing Completeness

Ethereum's programming language, Solidity, is Turing complete, which means it can perform any computation that can be expressed algorithmically. Bitcoin's scripting language is intentionally limited to prevent certain types of potentially harmful or resource-intensive computations. Ethereum's Turing completeness allows for a broader range of applications and complexity in DApps and smart contracts.

The term "Blockchain 2.0" is often associated with Ethereum, emphasizing its evolution beyond the simple transfer of digital currency. Ethereum introduced a new era of blockchain technology by enabling

programmable contracts and decentralized applications, greatly expanding the scope of what could be achieved with distributed ledger technology.

Ethereum's introduction of DApps opened the door to a wide range of decentralized applications. DApps operate on the Ethereum blockchain, utilizing smart contracts to automate processes and transactions. This has led to the emergence of a vibrant ecosystem of applications, including DeFi platforms, NFT marketplaces, and decentralized governance systems.

Despite its numerous achievements, Ethereum has faced challenges, particularly in terms of scalability and high gas fees. The increasing demand for Ethereum's services led to congestion on the network, resulting in higher transaction costs. These challenges prompted the development of Layer 2 scaling solutions like Polygon to alleviate these issues.

In order to improve the scalability, energy efficiency, and security concerns associated with the original PoW consensus mechanism, Ethereum has been undergoing a significant upgrade known as Ethereum 2.0. In this second version, Ethereum is transitioning to a PoS consensus mechanism, where validators are chosen to create new blocks based on the amount of cryptocurrency they hold and are willing to "stake" as collateral. This transition is expected to improve network efficiency and reduce its carbon footprint.

In summary, Ethereum represents a pivotal point in the evolution of blockchain technology, expanding its capabilities beyond the limitations of Bitcoin. With the introduction of smart contracts and DApps, Ethereum has opened up new possibilities in a wide range of industries, making it a foundational pillar of the blockchain ecosystem. Its ongoing transition to Ethereum 2.0, with a shift to PoS, underscores its commitment to sustainability and scalability, ensuring its continued relevance in the ever-evolving world of blockchain.

3.1.3 Layer 1 vs Layer 2 – Polygon

Ethereum and Bitcoin are considered Layer 1 blockchains. Layer 1 refers to the primary blockchain layer where the core network operates, transactions are processed, and security is maintained. Layer 2, on the

other hand, is a secondary layer built on top of Layer 1, designed to enhance scalability and reduce transaction costs by processing transactions off the main blockchain while benefiting from its security.

“A layer 2 refers to any off-chain network, system, or technology built on top of a Layer 1 blockchain that helps extend the capabilities of the underlying base layer network. Layer-2 networks can support any blockchain to introduce enhancements such as higher transaction throughputs.[3]

One core requirement for a network, system, or technology to be considered a layer 2 is that it inherits the security of the blockchain it is built on top of. Transaction data must, in some shape or form, be verified and confirmed by the underlying blockchain network rather than a separate set of nodes. For example, sidechains are often not considered as Layer 2s because they usually deploy their own consensus mechanisms and validators, leading to a different set of security guarantees than that of the base layer chain.

For blockchains that sacrifice scalability to achieve higher decentralization and security, Layer 2s enable greater transaction throughput, which can lead to lower fees. Layer 2s can be seen as one solution to the problem of scalability, enabling fast and scalable execution without compromising on decentralization or security.” [3]

Layer 2 solutions aim to alleviate congestion and make blockchain networks more efficient for various applications, including Decentralized Finance (DeFi) and Non-Fungible Tokens (NFTs).

The main Layer 2 blockchain built on top of Ethereum is Polygon [4].

Polygon provides a framework for creating Ethereum-compatible blockchains which process transactions more quickly and at a lower cost compared to the Ethereum main net. Polygon’s MATIC token is central to its ecosystem, serving various purposes, including paying transaction fees, and participating in network governance.

Polygon has gained prominence in the blockchain space due to its utility in a wide range of use cases.

Notable applications include:

- Decentralized Finance (DeFi), DeFi platforms, which enable financial services like lending, borrowing, and trading without traditional intermediaries, benefit from Polygon’s scalability and cost-effectiveness. Users can engage with DeFi protocols on Polygon with significantly lower transaction fees compared to the Ethereum main net.
- Non-Fungible Tokens (NFTs), unique digital assets often used for digital art, collectibles, and gaming, have experienced explosive growth. Polygon’s low transaction costs make it an attractive choice for creators and collectors, as minting, buying, and trading NFTs become more accessible.
- Gaming, Blockchain-based gaming platforms have embraced Polygon due to its capacity for fast and efficient transactions. Gamers can interact with blockchain games without the delays and high fees that can hamper the user experience on other networks.

Layer 1 and Layer 2 blockchain solutions offer distinct advantages and trade-offs:

Layer 1 Advantages

- Provide robust security and decentralization.
- Serve as the foundation for the entire blockchain ecosystem, hosting critical smart contracts and assets.
- Highly secure, backed by a large network of miners and validators.

Layer 2 Advantages

- Alleviate scalability issues by processing transactions off the main blockchain.
- Reduce transaction costs, making blockchain applications more accessible.
- can experiment with innovative consensus mechanisms, such as PoS, to improve efficiency.

3.1.4 Web3

The term “Web3” was coined in 2014 by Ethereum and Polkadot co-founder Gavin Wood [5] but the concept of Web3 started to take shape in the late 2010s as a way to describe a new vision for the internet. This vision leverages on decentralization, blockchain technology, and the empowerment of users in controlling their data and digital assets.

In the following years, the emergence of DeFi platforms and NFTs brought Web3 concepts into the mainstream. DeFi projects offered financial services like lending, borrowing, and trading on blockchain networks, while NFTs enabled to manage the ownership and trade of unique digital assets.

In addition, various projects and protocols have continued to develop the infrastructure for Web3, including decentralized storage systems (like IPFS), decentralized identity solutions, and blockchain networks designed for smart contracts and DApps.

In the meanwhile, communities and organizations focused on Web3 have emerged, with an emphasis on open-source development, decentralized governance models, and the promotion of user empowerment and privacy.

The Web3 concept and technologies are changing the way the creative world operates and creating new opportunities for artists and collectors alike.

The most important benefits that Web3 application can bring to the creative industry are:

- Democratization. Traditional creative industry is often only accessible to a select few, due to the high cost and exclusivity of owning physical work.
- Monetization. The ability for creatives to monetize their work in new ways. With NFTs, creative works have a unique digital signature, making it one of a kind and giving it value. Artists can now sell their digital assets as NFTs, creating a new revenue stream for them.

3.2 Blockchain in Creative Industry

In the current landscape of centralized digital platforms and intermediaries wielding substantial control over user data and content, prosumers frequently grapple with limited ownership and control of their digital assets.

DAFNE+, on the other hand, embraces a decentralized paradigm infused with blockchain technology. This transformation empowers prosumers by endowing them with greater ownership and control over their data, content, and digital assets. The immutable and auditable nature of blockchain technology ensures transparency in transactional data, thereby bolstering trust between creators of NFTs, NFT Marketplaces, and the end user/purchaser of NFTs. Peer-to-peer transactions, facilitated by blockchain, pave the way for diverse monetization avenues, including microtransactions and decentralized marketplaces.

Moreover, DAFNE+ serves as a catalyst for innovation and creativity. It equips prosumers with tools and technologies to experiment with fresh business models, services, and applications, free from the constraints imposed by centralized authorities or platforms that have merely transplanted existing models into a new technological realm.

Notable examples of these blockchain platforms that harness technology to bypass intermediaries are as follows:

- Steemit [6]: A blockchain-based social media platform that remunerates prosumers in cryptocurrency for content creation and curation.
- SuperRare [7]: A marketplace for digital art, employing NFTs to enable artists to monetize their digital creations directly.
- Async [8]: Tailored for musicians, this blockchain-based platform empowers artists to publish their work, assert ownership rights, and receive direct payments from customers.
- Audius [9]: A decentralized music streaming service that liberates musicians from intermediaries, allowing them to share their music directly with listeners.

- LBRY [10]: A decentralized platform for content publishing, which enables content creators to release their work directly without intermediaries.

While these platforms underscore the value of circumventing intermediaries, DAFNE+ is poised to revolutionize the creative industries by simplifying blockchain adoption, enabling the formation of DAOs, fostering innovative business models, enhancing legal transparency, nurturing communities, and driving creativity and competitiveness. The project's central aim is to empower content creators, enabling them to seize control of their work, engage with their audiences, and equitably reap the benefits of their creative pursuits.

Additionally, several proposals explore the use of blockchain and tokens in creative industries such as digital fabrication. For instance, the Interfacer EU project [11] developed a platform to register and track designs, products and services using a ledger, and store information about the contributors, place of production, materials and more. DAFNE+ will explore new business models to support creative communities such as makerspaces and fablabs, fostering the adoption of blockchain technology to support them.

3.3 Non-Fungible Tokens (NFTs) - Concept and main applications

With the emergence of Ethereum, that inserted programmatic ability in the blockchain realm, new standards started to appear. Ethereum standards provide guidelines and technical documentation for implementing new functionalities and features in smart contracts. They outline precise rules that the smart contract developer must follow to ensure the compatibility of applications within the network. One of the most prevalent standards is ERC-721 [12], which describes NFTs.

Fungibility, as a concept, refers to the ability to exchange assets interchangeably, while maintaining parity of perceived value. Examples of fungible assets include currencies and gold. For example, a dollar is indistinguishable from and interchangeable with any other dollar. Ethereum supports a standard to create fungible tokens, namely ERC-20 [13]. Non fungible assets on the other hand, include the concept of

uniqueness, and therefore cannot be exchanged. As an example, having two artworks, these have unique attributes, and possibly different kinds of value. Therefore, exchanging two artworks could lead to one party of the transaction having “less” while the other has “more”. The ERC-721 standard was the first standard to arrive that set the rules for creating Non-Fungible Tokens, or NFTs. Today, new standards have appeared, like ERC-1155, an upgrade of ERC-721, as well as standards implementing NFTs for other blockchain networks like PSP-34 for Polkadot [14].

NFTs are unique tokens, identified by a “token id”, as described in ERC-721, that are connected to an asset through a set of metadata. ERC-721, provides an API to:

- a. Create NFTs
- b. Transfer NFTs
- c. Gain insights such as:
 - Learn who owns a specific token.
 - Get the supply of such tokens in the network.
 - Find the balance of a specific account in terms of NFTs.

NFTs at their core act in a way as a validation of the ownership of a specific asset, that is transparent widely across the blockchain network. Also, provided the tokens are uniquely identified by the “token id”, they can also allow the tracking of the ownership of a token. NFTs can reference any type of item, physical or digital. From artworks and photos to real estate, the possibilities are constantly expanding. For instance, NFTs could be linked to:

- Images (photography or artworks)
- Videos
- Audio and music
- Tickets and coupons
- Software

- 3D models
- Physical objects

The world of NFTs made global headlines and became quickly renowned due to the enormous prices of some NFT artworks and collectibles sold. The first project bringing NFTs to the spotlight was the Cryptokitties project [15], a crypto-collectible game that allowed users to collect unique digital cats. NFTs present a diverse array of advantages to both creators and buyers:

- They empower creators by equipping them with tools to manage the ownership and copyright of their works.
- They allow creators to gain income from the reselling of their works on the secondary market with standards like ERC-2981: The NFT royalty standard.
- They can ensure the authenticity in the origin of works, through the transparent tracking of ownership mechanism.
- They allow for a way to transact digital or physical assets, in a secure and trustless way, breaking down geographical barriers.
- They give the opportunity to buyers to directly support their favourite artists and creators.

A broad spectrum of applications exists, encompassing different aspects of NFTs. The domain includes:

- **Applications for NFT creation:** these include tools that allow users without technical knowledge to create NFTs from their works. A popular example is Fotor [16].
- **Applications for NFT exchange:** these include NFT marketplaces, places where users can list and buy NFTs. One of the most popular examples is the OpenSea marketplace [17].
- **NFT games:** new types of games have emerged that include the NFT technology. These games allow the users to collect assets or in-game items in the form of NFTs. For example, one of the most renowned games is Axie Infinity [18].

-
- **Governance:** NFTs can represent voting rights in Decentralised Autonomous Organisations. These are organisations that are governed by smart contracts and not people. Every organisation sets its rules in smart contracts. These rules define among other things, the membership eligibility criteria. Some DAOs choose to set NFTs as the way for an individual to obtain membership.

4 Blockchain in DAFNE+ ecosystem

4.1 Blockchain Realm

The DAFNE+ Blockchain Realm consists of a blockchain-ready framework able to:

- Make simple and fast interactions with blockchain networks (Polygon and Ethereum)
- Facilitate the deployment and integration of Smart Contracts
- Provide APIs for blockchain core features (NFTs, Tokens, Smart Contracts methods, Monitoring, etc.)

The Blockchain Realm was integrated in DAFNE+ Application Layer and in particular in the NFT Marketplace and in the Content Management for accessing the Smart Contracts features and interacting with the blockchain network.

Figure 1 below shows the high-level architecture of the Blockchain Realm.

FIGURE 1: BLOCKCHAIN REALM ARCHITECTURE

The Blockchain Realm is a dockerized component which consists of two layers:

- **Service Layer**, that implements the Smart Contracts (Solidity), the Business Logic and the interfaces (based on Nodejs) for the Application Layer.
- **Blockchain API Services**, that implements the APIs (Web3.js) for interacting with the selected blockchain networks in order to deploy new Smart Contracts and call Smart Contracts methods.

4.1.1 Infrastructure and Networks

The Blockchain Realm main goal is to provide an interface between the DAFNE+ ecosystem and blockchain infrastructure.

Following the requirements elicited in D2.1, in the DAFNE+ context two different Blockchains were integrated: Ethereum and Polygon.

Ethereum and Polygon blockchains both support the minting and trading of NFTs, one of the main goals of the DAFNE+ Platform.

When these NFTs are minted or purchased, the transaction must be processed by a validator. This process requires energy, and using the blockchain implies computation which users pay for through a mechanism called a gas fee.

There is a strict relationship between gas fees and demand, therefore the greater the demand, the higher the gas fees and vice versa. Additionally, gas fees are higher during peak periods of computation when the chain has high utilisation; therefore, it is advisable to purchase NFTs during the less productive hours of the day when transaction/gas fees are lower.

Over time, there have been congestion issues due to limitations of block capacity on the Ethereum blockchain. These problems make gas fees expensive. This is where Polygon comes in for providing a solution to Ethereum cost problems.

Polygon aims to make it easier for people to access and use Ethereum by providing a scaled-up version of the Ethereum network with lower fees and faster transaction times. While there may be uncertainty about Polygon's role in the future once Ethereum completes its upgrades, Polygon currently serves a valuable purpose in the cryptocurrency ecosystem by helping bring more people in by providing scalable solutions for web3.

In the DAFNE+ Platform, the Creator is able to import digital assets, mint and sell NFTs on Polygon or Ethereum depending on their own specific needs and priorities. Polygon offers low gas fees and a growing market, Ethereum can offer more liquidity and user participation.

In the first release of the DAFNE+ Platform, in the scope of the validation phase with early adopters two testnets were selected and integrated in the Blockchain Realm. In this way, the end-users will be able to select the network more congenial to their needs and at the same time will allow us to test and collect feedback on the use of both layer 1 and layer 2.

Testnets are blockchains designed to mimic the operating environment of a mainnet but exist on a separate ledger. These testnets help developers test their applications and smart contracts in a risk-free way before deploying their products to the mainnet environment.

Ethereum Testnet - Sepolia

The Ethereum testnet used in DAFNE+ Platform is Sepolia.

Sepolia was a proof-of-authority testnet created in October 2021 by Ethereum core developers and maintained ever since. After the Ropsten testnet reached a very high Terminal Total Difficulty (TTD), the Sepolia test net transitioned to a PoS consensus mechanism to mimic the Ethereum mainnet.

Sepolia was designed to simulate harsh network conditions, and has shorter block times, which enable faster transaction confirmation times and feedback for developers.

Main information:

- Network Name - Sepolia Test Network
- Chain ID - 11155111
- Currency Symbol - SepoliaETH
- Block Explorer URL - <https://sepolia.etherscan.io/>

Polygon Testnet - Mumbai

The Polygon testnet used in DAFNE+ Platform is Mumbai.

The Mumbai testnet is the Polygon network’s testnet, a replication of the main Polygon network. It makes it possible for developers to test, launch, and run their DApps without risk or expense in the blockchain environment.

Mumbai employs a PoS consensus mechanism to determine the state of the blockchain, just like Polygon, which launched in 2017.

Main information:

- Network Name – Mumbai Testnet
- Chain ID - 80001
- Currency Symbol -Matic
- Block Explorer URL - <https://mumbai.polygonscan.com/>

4.1.2 Smart Contracts and main features

Smart contracts will keep track of all the media asset interactions expected in the DAFNE+ use cases and applications, including the usage of tools and libraries, the creation or adaptation of a media content item and its provision to the decentralized platform on behalf of the creators, the access and download on behalf of the consumers. The smart contracts will also allow for fine-grained monitoring and management of these actions as well as their translation in tokenized-based values.

In the first release of the DAFNE+ Blockchain Realm, three main features have been implemented in the Smart Contracts and integrated with the Content Management Tool:

- Import of content and declaration of ownership
- Digital asset management and definition of revenue models
- Logging Transaction (Creation, Usage, NFT creations, Sales, Distribution, etc...)

Import Digital Asset

Each time new content is imported into the DAFNE+ platform (see D4.2 for additional details) a new Smart Contract is created into the Blockchain Realm and linked to the imported content. The workflow is shown in the Figure 2 below.

FIGURE 2: IMPORT CONTENT WORKFLOW

The Smart Contract is deployed starting from a predefined one that implements the following attributes:

- Ownership (address of content's owner)
- Creation Time (the timestamp of the content creation in the Blockchain Realm)
- CID (Content Unique Id)
- URL (Link to the real content)
- Contributors List (List of addresses of the Contributors)
- Contributors Percentage (The percentage of contributions which define the revenue)

- Asset Tokens (ERC20 Tokens assigned for the redistribution)

It also implements the following methods:

- Add Contributor – Add a new contributor to the list and a related revenue percentage.
- Edit Contributor – Edit the percentage of a contributor.
- Remove Contributor – Remove a contributor from the list.
- Redistribute revenues – Distribute tokens based on the percentage of revenue in the contributor list.

Digital Asset Management

After the creation of a specific smart contract linked to each content of the DAFNE+ Platform, the Creator is able to define a basic method of revenue sharing model.

In this first release of the Blockchain Realm and the DAFNE+ Platform, the Creator/Owner is able to assign percentages of contributions to a group of contributors that will be notified about the assigned revenue.

The Creator/Owner can:

- Add contributors to the list (with specific revenue percentage)
- Edit the percentage of a contributor.
- Remove a contributor from the list.

Any of this action is notified to the contributors and registered into the Smart Contract of the Digital Asset, using the related methods stated above.

In case the Digital Asset is minted into NFT and made available for sale, the related method for the redistribution of the self-executed and the ownership of the Digital Asset updated accordingly. Figure 3 below shows this process.

FIGURE 3: REVENUE MODEL WORKFLOW

Logging Transaction

An additional Smart Contract was implemented for logging any transaction on the Digital Asset in order to track any usage or change of the Digital Asset.

More in detail the following actions are tracked:

- Creation of the Digital Asset (imported into the DAFNE+ ecosystem)
- NFT minting
- NFT Sale (and redistribution)

- Access/Usage of the Digital Asset

4.1.3 NFT Tool

The NFT tool is a utility component to the NFT marketplace. Its role is to handle the wrapping of items on the marketplace as NFTs as well as the exchange of NFT assets. The NFT tool service exposes endpoints that can be consumed by the internal DAFNE+ services such as the marketplace.

Ethereum currently utilises two standards that describe NFTs. ERC721 [11], the Non-Fungible Token standard that was the first to emerge and is the most widely used. And the ERC1155 [18] that is the Multi Token standard. ERC1155 was introduced as an enhanced and optimised version of its predecessor ERC721, that allows the creation of both fungible and non-fungible tokens.

Under the context of DAFNE+ the ERC1155 was selected as the standard to create NFTs, and the reasons are outlined below:

- It offers flexibility by allowing for the creation of both fungible and non-fungible tokens.
- It offers enhanced security in comparison to the ERC721 standard, for example it interfaces a function for secure transfers.
- It offers flexibility with the metadata.
- It allows for batch transfer of tokens, making it more cost and energy efficient.

One of the main functionalities of the NFT tool is to create transaction objects that will allow the minting of an NFT to a user account. The workflow is depicted in Figure 4.

FIGURE 4: NFT CREATION WORKFLOW

The tool uses the NFT data as specified by the user during the creation of an NFT in the marketplace, specifically:

- The name of the NFT
- A short description of the NFT
- The supply
- The price of the NFT
- A URL pointing to an image that displays the NFT
- Optionally, a URL that can be used by the NFT creator to point to their personal website or blog
- The type of asset the NFT corresponds to, including usual media (text, image, video, sound file) or more complex data types (components, repositories and others, as specified in use-cases).

- The license the NFT will be distributed with
- The user address to mint the NFT to

The data outlined above, are used to create the metadata of the NFT. An example depicting the structure of the metadata is depicted in Figure 5. The structure is compliant with the metadata standard of the OpenSea marketplace, in order for it to be able to correctly display NFTs created on the DAFNE+ platform and allow the users to sell their work there if they choose.


```
1  {
2    "name": "3D Artwork",
3    "description": "A 3D artwork of Ethereum symbol.",
4    "external_url": "https://unsplash.com/@dvliden",
5    "image": "ipfs://bafybeielwp3dst2sc5onaxbjjyaigxqabcwvx07hcowrze4souolly6weq",
6    "animation_url": "",
7    "attributes": [
8      {
9        "trait_type": "Media",
10       "value": "3D"
11     }
12   ],
13   "type": "3D",
14   "unlockable_content": "True",
15   "license": "Royalty Free License"
16 }
```

FIGURE 5: NFT METADATA

The tool, using the data provided by the user on the marketplace, creates a JSON file for the metadata of the NFT that it publishes on IPFS, a decentralized storage as described in D4.2. Afterwards, it creates the NFT smart contract based on a template contract that employs the ERC1155 standard, and specifying the metadata previously created. Finally, the tool builds the transaction object to deploy the smart contract and is going to be used by the marketplace.

Furthermore, the NFT tool includes as well other complimentary functionalities as outlined below:

- Checking if a user wallet address is the owner of a specific NFT
- Publishing files on IPFS and returning a relevant link

For the first release of the DAFNE+ platform, the aim is to validate the basic concept and ideas of DAFNE+. Therefore, the NFT tool initially focuses on implementing a flexible and basic structure that can be the basis for implementing new and more complex features in the future versions.

The design and architecture of the NFT tool as foreseen, will optimise the initial architecture in terms of cost and energy by implementing a proxy schema, where the logic and storage of the NFT contracts will be separated, while implementing as well, upgradeability features.

4.2 NFT Marketplace

DAFNE+ is offering a marketplace for users to exchange their content and artistic creations. It will work as a place where digital artists and creators can advertise and sell their work, while being enumerated fairly.

The DAFNE+ marketplace features:

- **The marketplace landing page:** where users can view all the marketplace items (Figure 6)
- **The user portfolio:** where users can advertise themselves and their work (Figure 7)
- **A wish list:** where users can save items they like
- **A cart:** where users can add items they wish to buy

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FIGURE 6: NFT MARKETPLACE LANDING PAGE

FIGURE 7: NFT MARKETPLACE PORTFOLIO

The marketplace landing page is the place where the user has access to a preview of assets and promotion materials featured in DAFNE+. They can personalise the search towards their need by applying filters based on:

- a. The type of asset, for example, image, 3D models, software component or work repository.
- b. Specific tags related to the content, for example, the user could search for artwork NFTs by applying the tag “video”, or “Van Gogh style”.

Also, the user can search for specific items using the name of the NFT they wish to find, or they can order the items from the most popular to the least, and from the most recent to the oldest.

FIGURE 8: NFT DETAILS

Furthermore, they can click on an item that they find interesting and be provided with more information about this item, like for example a short description about the NFT, maybe an external link to the creator’s personal blog and the list of tags applied to the specific item. These contents are referred to as “promotional materials” in the use-case scenarios.

If the user considers buying the item and they wish to safekeep it for later, they can “like” it, and it is automatically added on their personal wishlist. Later, they can visit the wishlist page where they can edit it by removing the items, they no longer find interesting.

From the marketplace page or from an item's page, the user can also add items to their cart, from where they can later proceed to buy using their web3 wallet.

For users that wish to create their creations as NFTs, the marketplace also features a plus button which can use to create a new NFT. The creation of an NFT process features the following steps:

- i. The user selects the type of asset they want to create as NFT and uploads their files. It is worth noting that users may also create NFTs from content they have already uploaded on DAFNE+, using the content manager. This process is described in D4.2.
- ii. The user specifies how they wish to distribute their content, if they want to create an NFT or to distribute the item for free. This choice will alter the flow of the following steps.

If the user chose to create a free item, then the process continues as:

- iii. The user inserts basic information to create a listing on the marketplace, like a title and a description.
- iv. The item is created and featured on the marketplace where users can download it.

If the user chose to create an NFT item, then the process continues as:

- iii. The user is prompted to connect to their Metamask wallet.
- iv. The user inserts details specific to the NFT, as the name, description, price and supply, as well as the license they wish to distribute it with.
- v. The user inserts details specific to the listing on the DAFNE+ marketplace, as for example different displaying options for the NFT. As well as apply tags to their item. These tags can be specified by the user, or they can select tags recommended by to them by the NFT content analysis tool of DAFNE+. The NFT content analysis tool and the related business process are described in D4.2.
- vi. Finally, the item is minted to their wallet and added on the DAFNE+ marketplace.

The entire process is shown in the Figure 9 below.

FIGURE 9: NFT CREATION ACTIVITY DIAGRAM

Licensing: DAFNE+ will allow the users to select the license with which they wish to distribute their content from a predefined list. The list of licenses will be the outcome of the work of WP6 and will offer the user the flexibility to select among a link of licenses. In the first version, a limited set of licensing options will be supported.

Unlockable content: The DAFNE+ marketplace will give the option to NFT creators to share unlockable content with their NFTs. The buyer or buyers of the NFT will then be able to visit the item on the marketplace again and unlock content private only to them. The unlockable content will be provided as text, but it can be:

- A link to a high-quality image of an artwork for an NFT representing a painting.
- Coupons or redeem codes unlocking special content.
- A link to private repository for NFT representations of software.

The possibilities are up to the NFT creator to decide. However, the unlockable content feature is part of the DAFNE+ marketplace, meaning that the unlockable content will not be provided for sales outside of DAFNE+. However, users that have purchased the NFT in external markets will have the possibility to access the unlockable content, by visiting DAFNE+ as the NFT owners.

Future version: In the future versions of the platform, the marketplace will offer new functionalities such as:

- It will give the option to creators to set a royalty, so that creators can benefit from the reselling of their works on the secondary market. The functionality will be implemented according to the ERC2981, which is the NFT Royalties standard.
- It will give the NFT owner the option to sell their NFT either by setting a fixed price, as implemented in the first version, or by setting a timed auction as well.
- It shall give the NFT creator the option to create their NFT without paying for the gas cost, this will be paid by the buyer of the NFT. The “free minting” would make the process of creating an NFT more accessible to artists and creators. This possibility shall be confirmed in the framework of WP6 in conformance to the project’s business model.
- It will feature a reputation system that will act as an achievement system where users’ contribution will be measured, and they will have the possibility to be rewarded for them. Creators will have the ability to build their status in the platform through gathering badges that will be displayed on their DAFNE+ portfolios.
- It will give users the possibility of creating new versions of assets by extending or updating their content, provided that this possibility was foreseen by their creator.
- It will enable users to import versioned assets from external repositories such as GitHub.

4.2.1 Architecture, specifications and interfaces

The NFT Marketplace, as the DAFNE+ platform, consists of two layers: the application layer and the storage layer. The application layer itself is comprised of two main components:

- **The backend service:** It implements the logic of the marketplace and exposes an API interface along with a Swagger documentation. It is build using the Django framework.
- **The user interface:** It implements a user-friendly and intuitive front-end application based on React JS.

The storage layer consists of PostgreSQL database.

Figure 10 below shows the high-level architecture of the NFT Marketplace.

FIGURE 10: NFT MARKETPLACE ARCHITECTURE

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The marketplace is interfacing with several other services of DAFNE+ to provide its full functionality. Specifically, it is interfacing with:

- The Identity and Authentication component, that is described in D4.2, in order to gain access to information about the users of the platform.
- The NFT tool, in order to provide blockchain functionalities related to NFTs. The related business process is depicted in D4.2.
- The NFT content analysis tool, to provide recommendations about tagging to NFT creators.
- The Content Management System, that is described in D4.2, along with the related business process about the connection with the marketplace.

The backend service offers an API to expose its functionalities, that at the time of writing, consists of 36 endpoints. The API documentation is provided using the Swagger framework, as depicted in Figure 11.

FIGURE 11: NFT MARKETPLACE APIS

In the Table 1 below we provide an overview of some representative endpoints, implementing some core functionalities.

TABLE 1: NFT MARKETPLACE MAIN ENDPOINTS

NFT Marketplace		
Interfaces	cart/	
	Description	The interface allows the handling of the user’s cart. It covers functionalities related to the creation, editing and deletion of the cart.
	Protocol(s) used	HTTPS
	Methods	POST, GET, PUT, PATCH, DELETE
	Message	<p>POST/PUT/PATCH:</p> <pre>{ "items": [] }</pre> <p>GET:</p> <pre>{ "id": 0, "user": 0, "items": [],</pre>

		<pre> "items_list": "string" } </pre>
	nft/	
	Description	This endpoint handles the creation, editing and deletion of NFT, object on the side of the backend service.
	Protocol(s) used	HTTPS
	Methods	POST, GET, PUT, PATCH, DELETE
	Message	<p>POST/PUT/PATCH:</p> <pre> { "name": "string", "price": 0, "license": 0, "supply": 0 } </pre> <p>GET:</p> <pre> [{ "id": 0, "name": "string", "price": 0, </pre>

		<pre> "license": 0, "supply": 0, "creator": "string" }]</pre>
	marketplace-item/	
	Description	This interface exposes functionality related to the handling of items on the marketplace.
	Protocol(s) used	HTTPS
	Methods	POST, GET, PUT, PATCH, DELETE
	Message	POST/PUT/PATCH: <pre> { "name": "string", "description": "string", "type": "image", "owner": 0, "tags": [], "external_link": "string", "display_image": "string",</pre>

		<pre>"nft": 0, "unlockable_content": "string" } GET: [{ "id": 0, "name": "string", "description": "string", "type": "image", "owner": 0, "tags": [], "external_link": "string", "created": "2023-10- 12T13:17:07.658Z", "modified": "2023-10- 12T13:17:07.658Z", "views": 0, "display_image": "string", "nft": 0, "unlockable_content": "string" }]</pre>
--	--	--

4.2.1.1 Installation and configuration guidelines

Both applications are dockerised. Below are described the configuration and installation steps for each:

Marketplace Backend Application

- Create a `.env` file with the structured reported in Table 2

TABLE 2: MARKETPLACE BACKEND - ENVIRONMENT VARIABLES

KEY	VALUE
POSTGRES_HOST	Marketplace-postgres
POSTGRES_DATABASE	db
POSTGRES_USER	user
POSTGRES_PASSWORD	{POSTGRES_PASSWORD}
GUNICORN_CMD_ARGS	“-c backend/gunicorn.py”
ADMIN_PASSWORD	{ADMIN_PASSWORD}
REDIS_HOST	marketplace-redis
REDIS_PORT	6379
AWS_SECRET_ACCESS_KEY	{S3_BUCKET_SECRET_KEY}
AWS_SECRET_KEY_ID	{S3_BUCKET_ACCESS_KEY_ID}
AWS_STORAGE_BUCKET_NAME	{S3_BUCKET_NAME}

- Run the following command: `docker compose up --build -d`

Marketplace Frontend Application:

- Create a `.env` file with the structure reported in Table 3

TABLE 3: MARKETPLACE FRONTEND - ENVIRONMENT VARIABLES

KEY	VALUE
REACT_APP_AUTH_URL	{The URL of the authentication and identity management}
REACT_APP_AUTH_REALM	{The realm name}
REACT_APP_AUTH_CLIENT	{The client_id}
REACT_APP_AUTH_SECRET	{The client_secret}
REACT_APP_API	{The URL of the marketplace backend API}

- Run the following command: `Docker compose up -build -d`

5 Conclusion

Starting from the user requirements and scenarios described in WP2 and together with a deep analysis on the state of the art of the Blockchain Technology, DAFNE+ Platform blockchain-based components and tools have been implemented for the first release.

The Blockchain Realm offers an entry point for interacting with the main two Blockchain networks used for NFT minting and digital asset management, in Ethereum and Polygon.

All the blockchain-based functionalities of the DAFNE+ applications like NFT Marketplace and Content Manager leverage a solid blockchain-based framework which will be extended and improved in the next stage of the project.

In fact, after the integration of these components in the overall DAFNE+ Platform and the related release (described in D4.2), the first piloting phase can start for testing and validating the functionalities and tools implemented so far.

At the end of the first validation phase, all the blockchain-based components and tools will be enriched and improved following the feedback came out from the users and implementing the second wave of requirements as described in D2.1.

6 References

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